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THE DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY IS AN IMPORTANT STEP IN BUILDING A NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: In this article, the author covered the ultimate goal of the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", as well as the factors underlying the determination of the fundamental goals and priorities of reforms carried out in the near future. He touched upon the impact of institutional changes in the new Uzbekistan today on economic growth and the well-being of the population, as well as the purpose and essence of the implementation of reforms aimed at balanced development of the country.

Keywords: Institute, institutional changes, economic growth, living welfare of the population, transformation of the economy

СТРАТЕГИЯ РАЗВИТИЯ – ВАЖНЫЙ ШАГ В ПОСТРОЕНИИ НОВОГО УЗБЕКИСТАНА

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Аннотация: В этой статье автор осветил конечную цель указа президента Республики Узбекистан "О стратегии развития Нового Узбекистана на 2022-2026 годы", а также факторы, лежащие в основе

определения основополагающих целей и приоритетов реформ, проводимых в ближайшем будущем. Он коснулся влияния институциональных изменений в новом Узбекистане сегодня на экономический рост и благосостояние населения, а также цели и сути реализации реформ, направленных на сбалансированное развитие страны.

Ключевые слова: институт, институциональные изменения, экономический рост, уровень жизни населения, трансформация экономики

Completely new institutions were created in the socio-economic life of our country in the process of economic and institutional reforms implemented step by step from the first years of Uzbekistan's independence. At the same time, an institutional environment was formed, which includes official rules determining the conduct and development of society and economy. The established institutional environment as a general institutional model determining the development of the economy of Uzbekistan had a strong impact on ownership, production and distribution relations and the establishment of a new management system. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" made it possible to understand, first of all, the fundamental goals and priority directions of the reforms to be implemented in our country in the near future, as well as the factors that are the basis for determining these goals and directions. The ultimate goal of Uzbekistan's development strategy is to further increase the well-being of the people. In order to improve the well-being of the members of society, it is necessary to implement institutional reforms aimed at balanced development of the country, to transform economic sectors and develop entrepreneurship more intensively, to unconditionally ensure human rights and interests, and to form an active civil society. The world community today is going through a complicated and conflicting period. In particular, economic processes in all regions are intensifying and intensifying, economic competition is becoming more and more serious.

Transformational processes are taking place in the social life of the countries. The configuration in the geopolitical space of the world is acquiring a completely different content and form. Even the spiritual and cultural life of nations and peoples is undergoing fundamental changes. In such a situation, in order to achieve the development of the country and increase the well-being of the people, first of all, it is necessary to ensure the continuous and stable development of the economy, strengthen its competitiveness and resistance to threats, improve the institutions of civil society, and establish the rule of law and justice in the society. very effective reforms were implemented in various fields. These reforms led to an increase in the country's economic power, strengthening of its social stability, increase in its political influence, and renewal of its spiritual space. Now Uzbekistan has all the socio-economic opportunities to achieve new goals and raise the standard of living of citizens. The goal of the development strategy to increase the well-being of the people is determined based on these possibilities. In the development strategy, it is necessary to ensure the stability of the national economy, to achieve stable growth of economic sectors, to turn the digital economy into a driver sector, to improve the investment environment, to increase financial resources, to develop entrepreneurship, to develop socio-economic regions . measures to increase the export potential are planned. Such measures will create a basis for increasing per capita income from 4 thousand US dollars by 2030.

The Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 caused our country to enter a new stage in its development - the period of establishing New Uzbekistan and creating the foundations of the Third Renaissance. At the first stage of the economic reforms implemented at this stage, special emphasis was placed on institutional changes. Abandonment of centralized planning, production, financial flows and flows of material resources by the state required a new approach to economic management. As a result of structural changes in management, the tasks of management institutions have completely changed. The administrative

management system, its control and executive institutions were completely destroyed. Redistribution tasks and their mechanisms have been abolished.

In recent years, large-scale administrative reforms have been carried out to create an effective management system, which is considered an important condition for the establishment of New Uzbekistan. In particular, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 23, 2022 "On measures to implement the administrative reforms of the new Uzbekistan" is a broad way to fully implement the ambitious idea that the implementation of administrative reforms in our country "State agencies should serve our people, not the people". revealed. The ultimate goal of the presidential decree is to create a compact public administration system that meets modern requirements in the conditions of New Uzbekistan, to increase the responsibility of the heads of state bodies and direct their activities to efficiency by simplifying the processes of decision-making and consideration of issues.

As a result of the reforms, the structure of state bodies was optimized by 15% on average by reducing the non-sectoral tasks of state bodies and introducing digital technologies into their activities, as well as reducing the positions of 40 deputy heads in 26 state bodies and organizations.

In order to reduce bureaucratic obstacles and improve the system of providing public services to the population, about 30 types of licenses and permits were canceled, more than 70 public services were simplified, and the requirement of more than 60 documents by state organizations was canceled due to the introduction of modern management principles into the activities of state bodies.

The number of users of the "Electronic Government" system has exceeded 4 million, and through it, more than 130 information resources of state agencies have been created.

About 350 types of services have been provided online on the single interactive public services portal.

The successful implementation of large-scale reforms at the modern stage of the country's development requires the creation of a completely new and effective

system of public administration. One of the main reasons why our government pays serious attention to the implementation of administrative reforms is the further reduction of administrative influence on economic sectors and the development of a healthy competitive environment of management, the expansion of market mechanisms aimed at increasing the investment attractiveness of the country and the work activity of the population. The following are planned in this direction:

- limiting the creation of state-owned commercial organizations and reorganization of existing state enterprises in areas where the private sector is effectively operating;
- development of specific market mechanisms of state participation in economic activity;
- improvement of the legal and institutional basis of social and public-private partnership in solving socio-economic issues;
- some state functions private to the sector transfer _
- Local state authority bodies financial opportunities expansion , their role and responsibility increase _
- Territorial of organs leader personnel choose and from place to place to put issues local state authority bodies powers strengthen _

As part of the administrative reforms, the executive authorities, which are being transformed, will be able to operate efficiently based on the new requirements set forth in this Decree.

By increasing the financial and institutional independence of leaders, an effective system of working with regions will be introduced.

Institutional changes alleviate certain conflicts in society, allow conflict between economic agents to be resolved through compromise, and increase the influence of new mechanisms used by the government in macroeconomic policy.

In institutional change, it is important to find answers to two questions. These are the following:

a) successive new institutions during the transition period whether implementation will lead to economic growth;

b) introduction of new institutions during the period of stabilization of the pace of development is it appropriate?

In our opinion, institutional reforms are a continuous process. At the same time, it is necessary to constantly improve the existing institutions in order to meet the growing material and spiritual needs of the society as fully as possible.

In our country, it is necessary to strengthen the impact of institutional changes on economic growth and the improvement of the population's well-being. At the same time, it cannot be said that intensive factors of economic growth and institutional conditions are being used sufficiently. This requires bringing the initiated institutional reforms to their logical conclusion. Ensuring stable economic growth in the range of 5.0-6.0 percent creates a material basis for continuous increase of real incomes of the population of our country and significant improvement of the standard of living.

Measures aimed at strengthening the impact of institutional changes on ensuring economic growth are being taken in our country. Important reforms to achieve these goals were accelerated by the implementation of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 8, 2017 "On approval of the concept of administrative reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. PF-5185. In the concept, 6 main directions of fundamental reform of the public administration system were determined. Today, with this decree, the "Roadmap" that provides for more than 40 specific measures for the practical implementation of the norms of the concept of administrative reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan is approved and actively implemented. In addition, the activities of more than 100 state and economic management bodies have been reviewed for critical study of the state administration system and its fundamental reform, and the field is currently being improved from an organizational, structural and institutional point of view. As a result, administrative, economic and institutional reforms are gaining momentum. Also, additional conditions for ensuring economic growth are created, and the mobility and activity of society members is increasing. Institutional norms and mechanisms

create a basis for increasing the efficiency of factors affecting economic development, and create conditions for economic growth in the long term. Problems related to the formation of the institutional environment and the occurrence of institutional restrictions reduce the opportunities for economic development. Taking this into account, it is necessary to assess the quality of the institutional environment formed in the country on economic development and the impact of institutional changes on economic growth, as well as to improve the structure and mechanisms of institutions that stimulate sustainable economic development .

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